

LINEAR RESPONSE OF POLYCRYSTALS TO COUPLED FIELDS:
EXACT RELATIONS AMONG THE COEFFICIENTS

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Abstract:

The response coefficients of a polycrystal, made of domains of a uniaxial crystal, to coupled fields-such as in the thermoelectric or magnetoelectric effects-are not all independent. Only $6n$ constants are needed to determine all the $3n(3n+1)/2$ measurable constants of any such a polycrystal-given the constants of the single crystal. The constraints on $L_{(\alpha\beta)}^*$ -the response matrix of the polycrystal, for the space coordinate α, β -are $L_{(\alpha\beta)}^* (L^{||})^{-1} L^{\perp} - L^{\perp} (L^{||})^{-1} L_{(\alpha\beta)}^* = 0$, where L^{\perp} and $L^{||}$ are the principal response matrices of the single crystal. For two-field phenomena, the most general polycrystal of this kind can have, only 14 independent constants-when no information on the constants of the crystal is available-instead of the 21 of a general crystal.

There is obvious interest in determining the effective linear-response properties-such as the dielectric, magnetic permeability, conductivity, diffusion tensors etc. -of polycrystals made of a crystal whose principal constants are known. Much of the work in this vein has focused on obtaining bounds on the effective constants-given some information on the structure of the polycrystal^{1,2} (for example, that it is statistically isotropic). We shall discuss here effective properties, pertinent to the response of the polycrystal, that is made of a uniaxial crystal, not to the application of a single driving field-as in the example above-but to many coupled fields. As we shall show, in this case the response coefficients of the polycrystal must satisfy a number of relations among themselves, in which the response coefficients of the single crystal appear, but which are otherwise independent of the structure of the polycrystal itself.

Consider the coupled multifield linear-response properties of crystals: the application of driving fields to the material, induces in it fluxes $\vec{J} \equiv (\vec{J}_1, \vec{J}_2, \dots, \vec{J}_n)$ that are related linearly to the driving fields-the latter being derivable from potentials $\phi \equiv (\phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_n)$:

$$\vec{J} = -L \vec{\nabla} \phi. \quad (1)$$

Here, L is the $n \times n$ response matrix of the material. This description fits equilibrium

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phenomena such as the magnetoelectric effect, where the driving forces are magnetic and electric fields, and the fluxes are the displacement and magnetic-induction fields. It also fits nonequilibrium processes where the fluxes are currents, such as the thermoelectric effect, in which the potentials are, essentially, the temperature and electric potential; and the conjugate fluxes are, respectively, the heat and electric currents. Another such process is coupled multispecies diffusion, where the potentials are related to the concentrations and the fluxes are the conjugate particle-currents.

In anisotropic materials, the elements of L are spatial tensors (we shall work in three dimensions, but all the results are straightforwardly generalized to any number of dimensions). Thus,

$$J_{\alpha k} = -L_{\alpha\beta km} \partial_{\beta} \epsilon_m. \quad (2)$$

(Latin indices indicate the fields, while Greek ones are reserved for space coordinates.) We shall be dealing with two sets of submatrices of L : the space-tensor moduli, $L_{(km)}$, of the material; and the $n \times n$ matrices $L_{(\alpha\beta)}$: the response matrix of the α component of the currents to gradients applied in the β direction. Their elements are

$$L_{(km)\alpha\beta} = L_{(\alpha\beta)km} = L_{\alpha\beta km}. \quad (3)$$

Barring rare exceptions³, L is symmetric under the simultaneous exchange of the field and space indices:

$$L_{\beta\alpha mk} = L_{\alpha\beta km} \quad \text{or} \quad L_{(mk)} = \tilde{L}_{(km)}, \quad L_{(\beta\alpha)} = \tilde{L}_{(\alpha\beta)}. \quad (4)$$

In nonequilibrium phenomena this symmetry is assured by the Onsager relations⁴; in equilibrium processes it results from the structure of the governing energy function of the problem. The general response matrix thus has $3n(3n+1)/2$ independent elements.

We confine our attention to uniaxial crystals; these have principal axes-common to all the tensors $L_{(km)}$ -two of which are degenerate, and we choose them as the y and z axes; thus,

$$L_{(km)} = \text{diag}(l_{km}^{\perp}, l_{km}^{\perp}, l_{km}^{\parallel}). \quad (5)$$

Antimony and Bismuth are examples of uniaxial crystals showing an appreciable thermoelectric effect, and Chromium oxide is one with prominent magnetoelectric properties.

For convenience of expression we shall be speaking of crystals all along; all we assume, however, is that the building material is one with principal axes that are common to all the tensor moduli, and that two of the axes only are degenerate; the material needs not be a crystal.

Look now at the two $n \times n$ matrices $L^{\parallel} = L_{(zz)}$ and $L^{\perp} = L_{(xx)} = L_{(yy)}$ whose elements are:

$$L_{km}^{\parallel} = l_{km}^{\parallel} = L_{zzkm}, \quad L_{km}^{\perp} \equiv l_{km}^{\perp} = L_{xxkm}. \quad (6)$$

Clearly, L^{\parallel} and L^{\perp} are symmetric by virtue of eqs. (3)(6); they are also both positive definite. This has to do with the fact that, by its physical significance, the generating function $G \equiv \sum L_{\alpha\beta km} \partial_{\alpha} \epsilon_k \partial_{\beta} \epsilon_m = -\vec{J} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \epsilon$, has to be positive. In the nonequilibrium case, this function gives the entropy increase rate⁴; in the equilibrium case it is proportional to the energy function near the equilibrium state and has to be positive if the equilibrium is to be stable.

The crux of our argument rests on the fact that any two such real, symmetric, and positive-definite matrices (of the same rank) can be diagonalized, simultaneously, by a congruent transformation using a real matrix W :

$$WL^{\parallel} \tilde{W} = \lambda^{\parallel} \equiv \text{diag}(\lambda_1^{\parallel}, \lambda_2^{\parallel}, \dots, \lambda_n^{\parallel}), \quad WL^{\perp} \tilde{W} = \lambda^{\perp} \equiv \text{diag}(\lambda_1^{\perp}, \lambda_2^{\perp}, \dots, \lambda_n^{\perp}). \quad (7)$$

Note that W is, in general, not a unitary matrix, as indeed it cannot be if L^{\parallel} and L^{\perp} do not commute. Define now the eigenpotentials and eigenfluxes

$$\psi = \tilde{W}^{-1} \phi, \quad \vec{j} = W \vec{J}; \quad (8)$$

they satisfy

$$j_k^{\parallel} = -\lambda_k^{\parallel} \partial^{\parallel} \psi_k, \quad j_k^{\perp} = -\lambda_k^{\perp} \partial^{\perp} \psi_k, \quad (9)$$

and the response matrix in this basis is thus

$$\lambda_{\alpha\beta km} = \lambda_k^{\alpha} \delta_{\alpha\beta} \delta_{km} \quad (\alpha, \beta = \parallel, \perp): \quad (10)$$

the fields are thus decoupled in the eigenfields. The generating function is form-invariant under this congruent transformation: $G = -\vec{j} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \psi$. A similar diagonalization procedure underlies the choice of normal modes of small oscillations near equilibrium⁵ through the simultaneous diagonalization of the kinetic- and potential-energy quadratic forms.

If the crystal properties are described in axes other than the principal ones, the response matrix is not diagonal in the space indices but is still diagonal in the fields.

Consider now a polycrystal, made of a uniaxial crystal, by filling space with crystallites whose principal axes are arbitrarily oriented. The effective response matrix, L^* , of such a polycrystal can still not connect different eigenfields and so its representation, λ^* , in the eigenbasis must be of the form

$$\lambda^*_{\alpha\beta km} = \lambda^k_{\alpha\beta} \delta_{km}, \quad (11)$$

with $\lambda^k_{\alpha\beta}$ symmetric in α, β . This implies that only the $6n$ elements of $\lambda^k_{\alpha\beta}$ are needed to determine the $3n(3n+1)/2$ elements of L^* -which represent the effective response matrix in the original-"physical" -basis. The latter must then satisfy $9n(n-1)/2$ relations among themselves, that may contain the elements of L , the response matrix of the single crystal, but that are totally independent of the structure of the polycrystal.

These relations are obtained as follows: For every choice of space indices α, β , the $n \times n$ matrix $\Lambda^*_{(\alpha\beta)}$ whose elements are

$$\Lambda^*_{(\alpha\beta)km} = \lambda^*_{\alpha\beta km}, \quad (12)$$

is diagonal, It represents the response matrix of the polycrystal in the eigenbasis, and is related to the matrix $L^*_{(\alpha\beta)}$ -whose elements are $L^*_{(\alpha\beta)km} = L^*_{\alpha\beta km}$ -by the same congruent transformation:

$$\Lambda^*_{(\alpha\beta)} = W L^*_{(\alpha\beta)} W. \quad (13)$$

Now, $\Lambda^*_{(\alpha\beta)}$, λ^{\parallel} , and λ^{\perp} are all diagonal and thus all commute with each other. We can thus write trivially

$$\Lambda^*(\alpha\beta)(\lambda^{\parallel})^{-1}\lambda^{\perp} - \lambda^{\perp}(\lambda^{\parallel})^{-1}\Lambda^*(\alpha\beta) = 0. \quad (14)$$

Multiplying by W on the left and \tilde{W} on the right, and inserting $\tilde{W}\tilde{W}^{-1}$ and $W^{-1}W$ between the matrices, we get the relations we are after:

$$C[L^*(\alpha\beta), L^{\parallel}, L^{\perp}] = 0, \quad (15)$$

$$C(M_1, M_2, M_3) \equiv M_1 M_2^{-1} M_3^{-1} M_2 M_1.$$

To recapitulate the points underlying this derivation: (i) Any three matrices, M_1, M_2, M_3 that can be diagonalized simultaneously by a congruent transformation—for this it is necessary that they be symmetric—satisfy $C(M_1, M_2, M_3) = 0$. (ii) The physical input consists of the fact that the submatrices $L^*(\alpha\beta)$, of the response matrix of any polycrystal made of a uniaxial crystal, are diagonal in the eigenbasis of fields that is defined by the submatrices L^{\parallel} and L^{\perp} of the single crystal; hence, they are all diagonalized together.

Equation (15) involves nine matrix relations (one for each choice of α, β) each of which consists of $n(n-1)/2$ independent equations: the arguments of C in eq.(15) are all symmetric, and so C itself is antisymmetric, by construction, and has only $n(n-1)/2$ independent elements. When the single crystal is, in fact, isotropic; i.e., $L^{\perp} = L^{\parallel}$ the compatibility conditions reduce to identities and are devoid of any information.

Milgrom and Shtrikman⁶ have employed very similar arguments to cast constraints on the linear-response properties of two-phase mixtures of isotropic materials where similar relations are obtained among the response coefficients of the composites and involve the response matrices of the two components in place of L^{\parallel} and L^{\perp} in the present case; they also discuss, in some detail, the properties of these compatibility conditions.

The elements of L enter the compatibility conditions only through certain combinations whose number is, in general, smaller than the number of relations—so is the case, at least, when the polycrystal is anisotropic. These elements can then be eliminated, leaving us with relations among $L^*_{\alpha\beta km}$ that are independent of any knowledge of the crystal from which the polycrystal is prepared, beside the fact that it is uniaxial. Some of these material-independent relations appear in the form of symmetry of the linear-response coefficients of the polycrystal, as space tensors: Since λ^* in eq.(11) is symmetric in α, β and the transformation back to the physical basis acts only on the field indices, the tensors $L^*_{(km)}$ must be symmetric—a nontrivial information; these account for $3n(n-1)/2$ of the $9n(n-1)/2$ compatibility conditions. All the other material-independent relations can be obtained in the following way: Since all the matrices $L^*(\alpha\beta)$ —only six of them are independent because of the $\alpha - \beta$ symmetry—are diagonal in the eigenbasis, any three of them must satisfy the compatibility conditions.

$$C[L^*(\alpha\beta), L^*(\gamma\delta), L^*(\epsilon\eta)] = 0. \quad (16)$$

These relations are symmetric with respect to any permutation of the three argument matrices, and are identities when any two of the arguments are equal. Even those equations that remain after this is taken into account, are not all independent, but they do contain all the material-independent relations.

We now turn to some examples. When the polycrystal is isotropized, it has an effective response matrix L^* —whose $n(n+1)/2$ independent elements are scalars—which must satisfy eq.(15) with L^{\parallel}, L^{\perp} . There are no material-independent relations in this case.

In the most common case of two fields-such as the thermoelectric and magnetoelectric effects-there are, altogether, nine compatibility conditions (that involve L^{\parallel}, L^{\perp}) one for each pair of space indices, leaving only twelve independent thermoelectric coefficients for an arbitrary polycrystal of a uniaxial crystal, when L^{\parallel}, L^{\perp} are given. These can be written, conveniently, as

$$\begin{vmatrix} e(\alpha\beta) & m(\alpha\beta) & a(\alpha\beta) \\ e^{\perp} & m^{\perp} & a^{\perp} \\ e^{\parallel} & m^{\parallel} & a^{\parallel} \end{vmatrix} = 0. \quad (17)$$

Here,

$$L^{\parallel} = \begin{pmatrix} e^{\parallel} & a^{\parallel} \\ a^{\parallel} & m^{\parallel} \end{pmatrix}, \quad L^{\perp} = \begin{pmatrix} e^{\perp} & a^{\perp} \\ a^{\perp} & m^{\perp} \end{pmatrix}, \quad L^*(\alpha\beta) = \begin{pmatrix} e^*(\alpha\beta) & a^*(\alpha\beta) \\ a^*(\alpha\beta) & m^*(\alpha\beta) \end{pmatrix}, \quad (18)$$

are, respectively, the two principal response matrices of the single crystal, and the α, β response matrix of the polycrystal. The elements of L^{\parallel}, L^{\perp} enter these relations in two combinations that can be eliminated to leave seven crystal-independent relations. Three of these imply the symmetry $L^*(\beta\alpha) = L^*(\alpha\beta)$ (beyond the Onsager relations); the remaining four amounts to the six triplets $\{e(\alpha\beta), m(\alpha\beta), a(\alpha\beta)\}$ ($\alpha\beta = xx, yy, zz, xy, xz, yz$) being all in the same plane in the (e, m, a) space (the determinant of any three vanishes). The most general polycrystal, made of a uniaxial crystal, thus has only fourteen independent constants-when we have no information on L^{\parallel}, L^{\perp} -instead of the twenty-one that a general crystal has.

as a demonstration, we calculated, directly, the general multifield response matrix for a model isotropized polycrystal⁷. The basic element of the model is a spherical shell, of arbitrary proportions, in which the small domains of the single crystal are oriented with their \parallel -axis along the radius of the shell. Space is then filled with such shells of different proportions; then, these shells are filled from within, by other shells-not necessarily concentric with the one in which they are nested. We continue in this vein, in an infinite sequence of nestings, to fill the whole volume of space. This is a generalization of the model of Schulgasser² who calculated the effective coefficient for the special case of space-filling spheres, and for the single-field case. One then solves exactly for the effective response matrix, L^* , of such an isotropic medium and finds that it satisfies

$$L^*(L^{\parallel})^{-1}L^* - (d-2)L^* - (d-1)L^{\perp} = 0, \quad (19)$$

where d is the dimension of the problem. Multiplying by $L^{\perp}L^{*-1}$ on the left we get

$$L^{\perp}(L^{\parallel})^{-1}L^* - (d-1)L^{\perp}L^{*-1}L^{\perp} - (d-2)L^{\perp} = 0. \quad (20)$$

As all the matrices involved are symmetric, so is the right-hand-side of eq.(20) and so must the product on the left-hand-side be; this is, however, just the content of the compatibility conditions eq.(15) (remember that this condition is symmetric in the three arguments); as expected, L^* for this model satisfies the compatibility conditions.

The arguments we have presented do not extend-to our knowledge-to polycrystals of more general single crystals. This would have required the simultaneous diagonalization of three or more matrices which is not possible, in general (except for special cases where the three matrices are linearly dependent, for example, in which case our results still apply).

One interesting generalization pertains to the case where the polycrystal contains regions that are filled with either an ideal "insulator" -having $L=0$ -or an ideal "conductor"-for which the diagonal elements of L are infinite. In the former case all the

currents vanish in the regions occupied by the insulator (enclosures of vacuum will have this property in connection with the thermoelectric effect); this implies the appropriate zero-derivative boundary condition, in the crystals, at their boundaries with the insulator. In the case of an ideal "conductor" (such as enclosures of vacuum in the case of multispecies diffusion) all the potentials are constants on these boundaries. In either case the presence of the added material has a purely geometrical effect-entering, as it does, only through the location of the boundaries-and it certainly does not couple the eigenfields; all our results thus remain intact. (We assume that the added material does not percolate so as to render the effective properties trivial; e.g., if a conductor percolates in the direction along which the currents are measured, the polycrystal will have an infinite response.)

The question of polycrystals made of uniaxial crystals, that we have treated here, is not, altogether, divorced from that of two-phase mixtures discussed in ref. 6. One can prepare a material with uniaxial symmetry by forming very-thin-layer laminates of two isotropic components. The effective L^{\parallel} and L^{\perp} response matrices of the mixture are given, respectively, by the harmonic mean, and the mean of the response matrices of the two components. The composite made of small grains of such a laminate, is a special case of the sort of "polycrystals" we deal with in this paper. Not all the allowed L^{\parallel} , L^{\perp} can be obtained in this way because the means obey certain inequalities which L^{\parallel} , L^{\perp} need not obey. In the cases where this is possible, our results here can be shown to follow also from the results on two-phase mixtures.

All our results can be extended to the case of complex response matrices in a way that is described in ref. 6.

Clearly, results that have been derived elsewhere for uncoupled fields, can be applied to the eigenfields, and their meaning then expressed in terms of the "physical" fields. Take any result that is valid for the single-field case constituting an equality or an inequality involving the constants of the crystal and of the polycrystal. If this result holds for all the eigenfields, it can be written as a diagonal-matrix-relation. This relation has then to be written such as to have, on each side, an expression of the form $\dots \lambda^a (\lambda^d)^{-1} \lambda^c (\lambda^d)^{-1} \dots$, (both sides beginning and ending with the same power) where the λ 's are the diagonal response matrices in the eigenbasis, all of which transform in the same way. The same relation then holds in the physical basis, with the λ 's replaced by the L 's.

Other examples of such single-field results that call for a generalization to the multifield case are bounds on the effective constants^{1,2} and also improved simultaneous bounds on pairs of constants analogous to those found by Bergman^{8,9} for two-phase composites.

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REFERENCES

1. K. Schulgasser, J. Phys. C 10, 407 (1977); and more recently: M. Avellaneda, A.V. Cherkaev, K.A. Lurie, and G.W. Milton J. Appl. Phys. 63, (10) 4989 (1988), and many references therein.
2. K. Schulgasser, J. Appl. Phys. 54, 1380 (1983).
3. H.B.C. Casimir, Rev. Mod. Phys. 17, 343 (1945).
4. H.B. Callen Thermodynamics, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, (1960).
5. See, for example, H. Goldstein classical Mechanics Addison Wesley, Reading (1950). A detailed proof, in a context similar to the present one, can be found in ref. 6.
6. M. Milgrom and S. Shtrikmam, preprint (1989).
7. M. Milgrom and S. Shtrikmam, Preprint (1989).
8. D.J. Bergman, Phys. Rev. B 14, 1531 (1976).
9. D.J. Bergman, Phys. Rev. B 14, 4304 (1976).